

APPENDIX: LIST OF ITEMS USED IN STUDY

EMPLOYEE PERCEPTIONS OF CSR

(Turker, 2009)

1. Our company participates to the activities which aim to protect and improve the quality of the natural environment
2. Our company makes investments to create a better life for the future generations
3. Our company implements special programs to minimize its negative impact on the natural environment
4. Our company targets sustainable growth which considers the future generations
5. Our company supports the non-governmental organizations working in the problematic areas related to our industry
6. Our company contributes to the campaigns and projects that promote the well-being of society
7. Our company encourages its employees to participate in voluntary activities
8. Our company policies encourage the employees to develop their skills and careers
9. The management of our company is primarily concerned with employees' needs and wants
10. Our company implements flexible policies to provide a good work and life balance for its employees
11. The managerial decisions related to the employees are usually fair
12. Our company supports employees who want to acquire additional education
13. Our company protects client rights beyond the legal requirements
14. Our company provides full and accurate information about its services to its clients
15. Client satisfaction is highly important for our company
16. Our company always pays its taxes on a regular and continuing basis
17. Our company complies with the legal regulations completely and promptly

ORGANIZATIONAL PRIDE

(Gouthier and Rhein, 2011)

1. I feel proud to work for my company
2. I feel proud to contribute to my company's success
3. I feel proud to tell others for which company I am working

EMPATHETIC LEADERSHIP

(Kock et al., 2019)

1. My supervisor gives me praise for my good work
2. My supervisor shows me encouragement for my work efforts
3. My supervisor shows concern about my job satisfaction
4. My supervisor expresses his/her support for my professional development
5. My supervisor shows trust in me

COVID-INDUCED PERCEIVED JOB INSECURITY

(De Witte, 1999; Vander Elst et al., 2014)

1. Chances are I will soon lose my job due to covid-19 repercussions
2. I am sure I can keep my job despite any covid-19 repercussions
3. I feel insecure about the future of my job due to covid-19 repercussions
4. I think I might lose my job in the near future due to covid-19 repercussions

WORK ENGAGEMENT

(Schaufeli et al., 2002)

1. At my work, I feel bursting with energy
2. At my job, I feel strong and vigorous
3. I am enthusiastic about my job
4. My job inspires me
5. When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work
6. I feel happy when I am working intensely
7. I am proud of the work that I do
8. I am immersed in my work
9. I get carried away when I am working

ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

(Schappe, 1998; Smith et al., 1983)

1. While at work, I help others who have heavy workloads
2. I help others who have been absent
3. I willingly give my time to help others who have work-related problems
4. I take longer lunches or breaks
5. I take unnecessary time off work
6. I take extra breaks

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